

KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICE OF MOTHER TOWARDS EXCLUSIVE BREASTFEEDING

Healthcare

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Abstract

For the first six months of a baby's life, it is recommended that he or she be fed only human milk. Breastfeeding protects a baby's immune system and ensures that he or she grows and develops normally. The goal of a recent research was to examine nursing moms' knowledge and attitudes on exclusive breastfeeding. Dhaka, Mirpur-14, Marks Medical College & Hospital, where this research was done. Descriptive cross-sectional research was used in this study. A total of 115 nursing mothers who had just given birth were included in the study. In order to disseminate the questionnaire, a random sample method was used. SPSS Version-20 was used to analyze the data, and the results were presented in the form of a graph and a table. There were 100 percent females, 67 percent of whom were Muslim, and 100 percent of them were married. 49.6 percent of the respondents were class (HSC) qualified. Family income was 25060.87 Taka, with a standard deviation of 4672.215 Taka. Only 34(29.6 percent) of the lactating mothers began nursing within an hour of birth and 85.2 percent of the respondents gave the infant liquid breast milk during the first three days following delivery, according to the findings of the present research. During the prenatal period, 50.4 percent of respondents received counseling information from their families, the highest percentage in this research. Many participants in this study strongly agreed that breast milk should be fed to a newborn, 84.3 percent agreed that it protects the baby from illness, and 68.7 percent agreed that it should be the first feed given to a baby after birth. 70.4 percent said that breast milk alone can sustain the child for six months. This research shows that women have a strong understanding of the benefits of nursing exclusively. A large sample size is needed to describe the knowledge of the mother toward exclusive breastfeeding in the gynae ward patient department of Marks Medical College and hospital, Dhaka.

INTRODUCTION

Breastfeeding is a natural procedure that involves both exclusive and partial techniques, the latter of which is now the most popular. Exclusion, on the other hand, is the only strategy with the greatest potential for cascading effects. A successful conclusion will be achieved only when the mother and her infant work together harmoniously on all levels, including mental, emotional, and physical (Khresheh, 2011). Milk from a mother's breast contains It was the goal of this research to examine the knowledge and attitudes of primigravidas on exclusive breastfeeding, as well as to identify the probable problems faced throughout the exclusive breastfeeding phase. Despite government and non-governmental groups' best efforts, the rate of exclusive breastfeeding decreased. This prompted the researcher to look into the cause of these low percentages. With regular interaction with new moms and their babies, a nurse must have a high level of self-confidence to encourage, identify the value, inadequacies, as well as the relevance of exclusive breastfeeding to this vulnerable group of people Because this, a nurse's duty to assist, advise, and follow up on health professionals while adhering to ethical standards compelled the researcher to

focus on a specific issue. For this study, the researchers sought to equip nurses and other health care workers with the information they needed to better understand why new women stop nursing so soon after giving birth.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mothers' decisions and actions on IYCF are largely impacted by their understanding of the topic (Lutter, 2000). While Bangladeshi women believed that breast milk was beneficial for their children, they had a limited understanding of the health advantages of breast milk. 86% of women heard about EBF, however many understood it meant breast milk plus other liquids (typically water or cow's milk) during the first six months of the child's life. EBF was misunderstood by young women in Bangladesh, and they had a lack of understanding of when and how long to breastfeed, as well as unfavorable expectations about the amount of breast milk they would produce (Hackett et al., 2012). 87.3 percent of Ethiopian women were aware of EBF, whereas 12.7 percent of mothers had no awareness of EBF and began supplementing their baby's diet before the age of four months, believing that breast milk alone was insufficient (Wolde et al., 2014). Maternal knowledge and awareness did not convert into the practice of exclusive breastfeeding in Nigeria, according to a study (Onah et al., 14 2014). EBF knowledge differs between moms who have given birth several times and those who have not.

Among nursing women in Nairobi's Kibera slums, the level of breastfeeding expertise was found to be lacking. About two-thirds of the moms (65.3%) understood that kids should be nursed for at least two years; 88.3% recognized that newborns should be breastfed on demand. About a third (32.2 percent) of moms, on the other hand, said newborns should be exclusively breastfed for 1 to 3 months, whereas just 22.2% of moms said that was the case. EBF isn't influenced by a person's awareness of EBF, according to research (Ochola, 2008). Breastfeeding women in Kenya have been shown to have a high level of awareness about breastfeeding (Ogada, 2014). Breastfeeding moms in Wajir East and Wajir South had a high level of understanding about EBF, according to a KPC study (Save the Children, 2013).

Moreover, 87 percent of rural moms had a strong understanding of what exclusive breastfeeding entailed, yet only 30.5% of them continued to do it when their children were between four and six months old (Agu & Agu, 2011). Although the prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding among rural Jamaican mothers remains low at 22.2 percent, the findings of Chatman, Salihu, Roofe, Wheatle, Henry & Jolly (2004) show that there is no significant difference in knowledge and attitudes between mothers who exclusively breastfeed and those who do not.

34.8 percent of infants are breastfed during the first six months of life worldwide, with the remainder getting some other food or liquids during this period. Infants' energy and nutritional requirements are met throughout the first six months of life when exclusively breastfed. Data gathered from 64 nations, representing 69% of births in developing countries, also suggests that

the rate of exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life has improved from 33% to 37% between 1996 and 2006. Rates in sub-Saharan Africa rose from 22% to 30%, whereas in Europe they rose from 10% to 19%. There has been a rise in the proportion of newborns exclusively breastfed throughout Latin America and the Caribbean, excluding Brazil and Mexico, since 1996. More than half of Canadian women are exclusively nursing at 3 months, and 13.8 percent are still doing so at 6 months, according to research based on a maternity experience survey.

Objectives

General objective

➤ To assess knowledge of mothers who have recently delivered a baby towards exclusive breastfeeding.

Specific objectives

➤ To assess knowledge of the mothers who have recently delivered a baby toward, exclusive breastfeeding.

➤ To find out the socio-economic characteristics of the mothers who have recently delivered a baby.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Study design

Descriptive cross-sectional study

Study place

The study was carried out at Marks medical College & Hospital Dhaka.

Study population

The study population was the postnatal ward in Mark Medical Collage & Hospital Dhaka which has been selected due to the convenience of collecting data.

Selection criteria of the study population

The following criteria were used to select the respondents:

Inclusion criteria

- A lactating mother who is exclusively breastfeeding.
- Those lactating mothers will give consent and willing to participate in this study.

Exclusion criteria

- The mother who will not be mentally sound.
- Mather will be extremely sick.
- Mothers who are giving other food to the baby besides breastfeeding.

Study period

The study duration was 6 months from January 2018 to June 2018.

Sample size

Sample population will be calculated using the following formulae.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Where, n= The desired sample size

Z= Normal deviate 1.96 which corresponds to 95% confidence interval

p = Proportion of the target population estimated to have desired characteristics

P = 0.5 (50%) (Assumed)

q = 1-p (Proportion in the target population not having the desired characteristics)

q=0.5

d= Degrees of freedom=0.05

So, the sample size, $n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.05^2}$
 $= 384$

Therefore 384 samples will be taken for the study. But considering the time and resource constrain the sample size will be taken 115.

Sampling technique

Purposive sampling.

Data collection instrument

Semi-structured questionnaires were prepared for data collection. After developing the questionnaires, pre-testing was done. Following pre-testing, necessary modifications were done and the questionnaires were finalized for data collection.

Data collection and technique

Informed consent was taken from patients before an interview. Data was collected through the face-to-face interview by using a semi-structured questionnaire.

Data processing

At the end of a collection of data, all data is checked for its completeness, correctness, and internal consistency to exclude missing or inconsistency of data. After that coding categorization of data was done.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was done by using SPSS version 20. For analyzing data some descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, percentages were done. Data were presented through appropriate tables, graphs, charts, etc.

Ethical considerations

- ❖ The approval letter for the conduction of research on a specified topic was taken from the AIUB and Marks Medical College & Hospital Dhaka.
- ❖ Informed consent was taken from each respondent.
- ❖ Privacy confidentiality and anonymity were maintained.
- ❖ The nature and purpose of the study were explained.
- ❖ The respondent should have the freedom to take part in the interview.
- ❖ Refrain from answering any question.
- ❖ The research was good rather than any harm

RESULTS

This cross-sectional was undertaken among the patients attending at Gynae ward patient Department of marks Medical Collage Hospital, Dhaka with aimed to find out the knowledge of mothers toward exclusive breastfeeding. Information was collected by face-to-face interview thought structure and questionnaire. All collected data were cleaned, edited, and analyzed with the help of software- SPSS Windows Version 20. The analyzed data were presented through different Table and Graphs follow:

Table 1
Distribution of patients by age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-22	23	20.0
23-27	52	45.2
28-32	40	34.8
Total	115	100.0
Mean±SD	25.47 ± 3.447	

Figures above clearly demonstrate that, out of 115 participants, 23 respondents were between the ages of 18 and 22, 52 respondents were between the ages of 23 and 27, and 40 respondents were between the ages of 28 and 32, making up 34.8 percent of the entire population. In this study, the participants were all mothers who had recently given birth or were between the ages of 18 and 32, indicating that the duration of their real-life experiences in the workplace is strongly linked to the level of knowledge of the mother regarding exclusive breastfeeding in the hospital.

Figure 1

Distribution of patient by educational status

The above table shows that out of 115 respondents 49.6% (57 in Number) of the participants were completed their secondary level of education while 25.2% (29 in number) of the participants were completed their diploma level of education and 25.2(29 in number) were completed Degree.

Figure 2

Distribution of patients by religion

The above pie chart shows the total participants categorized according to their religions. The pie chart shows that out of 115 respondents almost 77(67%) participants were Muslims, 38(33%) participants are Hindus.

Figure 3

Distribution of patient by occupation

This figure shows that out of 115 respondents, about 40(34.8) were doing the job in a different sector while more than 75(65.2%) were housewives.

Table 4
Distribution of patients by monthly family income

Monthly family income	Frequency	Percent
Up to 20000	27	23.5
21000-25000	52	45.2
26000-30000	24	20.9
31000-35000	10	8.7
36000-40000	2	1.7
Total	115	100.0
Mean \pm SD	25060.87 \pm 4672.215	

This table shows that distribution of the respondent by monthly family income out of 115 respondents, 52(45.2%) were in the monthly income group 21000-25000TK. 27(23.5%) respondents were in the monthly income group 36000-40000TK. 24(20.9%) respondents were in the monthly income group 26000-30000TK. 10(8.7%) respondents were in the income group 31000-35000TK. And rest 2(1.7%) respondents were in the age group 36000-40000TK. Mean monthly family income was 25060.87 taka with $SD \pm 4672.215$ taka.

Figure 5
Distribution of patient by family type

The pie chart shows that out of 115 respondents maximum of 93(81.9%) were nuclear family and the rest were 22(19.1%) Joint families.

Table 6
Distribution of patients by number of births

Number of births	Frequency	Percent
Primi	39	33.9
Multi	76	66.1
Total	115	100.0

This table shows that out of 115 respondents maximum of 76(66.1%) were Multipara and the rest minimum 39(33.9%) were primi.

Figure 6

Distribution of patient by knowing about the mean of Exclusive breastfeeding

This figure shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 86(74.8%) were know about the meaning of exclusive breastfeeding. And rest of the 29(25.2%) respondents didn't know about the meaning of exclusive breastfeeding.

Table 7

Distribution of patients by receive counseling on Exclusive breastfeeding

Receive counseling on EBF	frequency	Percent
Yes	86	74.8
No	29	25.2
Total	115	100.0

This table shows that out of 115 respondents maximum of 87(74.8%) were received counseling on EBF and the rest minimum of 29(25.2%) were don't receive counseling on EBF.

Figure 8

Distribution of patient by the source of receiving counseling

This figure shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 34(29.6%) were receiving EBF counseling information from Family followed by 30(26.1%) were receiving EBF counseling from Media. Minimum of respondents17(14.8%) receiving EBF counseling from the Hospital.

Figure 9

Distribucion of patient by the time of received breastfeeding counseling

This figure shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 58(50.4%) were receiving EBF counseling information before delivery during antenatal clinic followed by 12(10.4%) were receiving EBF counseling during the postnatal clinic. 6(5.2%) respondents were receiving EBF counseling information after delivery. Minimum 5(4.3%) receiving EBF counselling at the time of delivery.

Table 10
Distribution of mother by breastfeeding the baby

Breastfeed the baby	Frequency	Percent
Yes	86	74.8
No	29	25.2
Total	115	100.0

This table shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 86(74.8%) were breastfeeding the baby. Minimum 29(25.2%) respondents were not breastfeeding the baby.

Figure 11
Distribution of mother by the time of first breastfeed after delivery

This figure shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 34(29.6%) were first breastfeeding the baby within 1 hour after delivery followed by 29(25.2%) were first breastfed the baby after 1 hour of delivery. Minimum 12(10.4%) respondents didn't remember the accurate time of first breastfeeding the baby.

Table 12
Distribution of mother by giving first three days liquid of breast after delivery

Give first three days liquid of breast	frequency	Percent
Yes	98	85.2
No	17	14.8
Total	115	100.0

This table shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 98(85.2%) were given the first three days of liquid of breast to the baby. Minimum 17(14.8%) respondents were not giving the first three days of liquid of breast to the baby.

Table 13

Distribution of mother by giving any liquid before first breastfeed

Giving another liquid	frequency	Percent
Yes	34	29.6
No	81	70.4
Total	115	100.0

This table shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 81(70.4%) were given any liquid before first breastfeed. Minimum 34(29.6%) respondents were not given any liquid before first breastfeeding the baby.

Figure 14

Distribution of mother by types of liquid was given without breast milk

This figure shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 14(12.2%) were given another liquid (formula milk) before first breastfeeding the baby followed by 12(10.4) was given another liquid (medicine). Minimum 7(6.1%) respondents were given another liquid (honey) before first breastfeeding the baby.

Figure 15

Distribution of mother by reason for giving another liquid

This figure shows that out of 115 maximum respondents 16(13.9%) were given another liquid before first breastfeeding the baby due to the infant being unwell followed by 15(13.0) were given another liquid due to the mother being unwell. Minimum 2(1.7%) respondents were given another liquid before first breastfeeding the baby due to delayed milk production from the mother.

Table 16

Distribution of mother by knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs on EBF

Attitude	Responses			
	Yes(F)	Percent	No(F)	Percent
Breastfeed should be the first feed a baby is given after birth	79	68.7	36	31.3
The baby should be put to the breast after more than one hour to allow the mother to rest	71	61.7	44	38.3
The first yellowish milk should be fed to the baby	110	95.7	5	4.3
Breast milk alone without even water can sustain the baby for six months	57	49.6	58	50.4
Breastfeeding helps the mother not to get pregnant	52	45.2	63	54.8
Breast milk protects the baby from illness	97	84.3	18	15.7
Total	499			

The above table shows the attitude of a mother who participated in the study. A set of questions were given to them to check their attitudes regarding exclusive breastfeeding. A total of 499 responses were found from 115 participants against 06 questions. The majority of the time (95.7%) respondents strongly agreed with the concept in terms of the first yellowish milk should be fed to the baby. (61.7%) participants shared that the baby should be put to the breast after more than an hour to allow the mother to rest. In(84.3%) cases participants shared that; breast milk protects the baby from illness.(68.7%) indicates the percentage of respondents who said breastfeeding should be the first feed a baby is given after birth.(49.6%) respondents said that breast milk alone even can sustain the baby for six months. (45.2%) respondents said that breastfeeding helps the mother not to get pregnant.

Discussion

This was cross-sectional descriptive research. An investigation of the knowledge of mothers toward exclusive breastfeeding of new mothers who just gave birth at the Gynae department of Marks Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, resulted in 115 participants aged 19 to 32 years old. The findings of this study may serve as a foundation for further research into the attitudes of new mothers toward exclusive breastfeeding at various Bangladeshi tertiary level hospitals' gynecology ward patient departments.34 of the respondents (29.6 percent) were the first to breastfeed their child. After 1 hour after birth, 29(25.2%) were the first to nurse the infant, followed by 29(25.2%) within an hour. A minimum of 12(10.4%) of the respondents were unable to recall the exact moment of the baby's first breastfeed. The results of this research are comparable to those of Alemayehu et al (2014) Breastfeeding began within one hour in 44.7 percent (98 of 115 maximum responses) in this research, with 85.2 percent supplying the first three days of liquid breast milk to their baby. A minimum of 17 (14.8%) of the respondents did not provide the infant with breast milk during the first three days of life. Similar to Alemayehu et al., (2014), 72.2 percent of the mothers were providing the kid other than breast milk in the first three days after birth. Majority More than nine out of ten of the people surveyed thought that the infant should be given its first yellowish milk. Alemayehu et al., (2014), found that the prevalence of timely commencement and EBF was 41.6 percent and 40.9 percent, respectively. 45 percent of the colostrum was discarded by the mother when she squeezed them out.

There were 14(12.2%) of the 115 respondents who had given the infant formula milk before breastfeeding, followed by 12(10.4%) who had given the baby formula milk (medicine). A minimum of seven (6.1 percent) of the respondents gave the infant a drink (honey) before breastfeeding. This research differs from Setegn et al in several ways (2012). Some 68.2% reported providing their infant's breast milk with supplementary food, such as chow milk (57.0%), cereal-based fluids (45.2%), and tea (23.9%) before the child was six months old. For the most part, primiparous women were more educated than multiparous women about the scientific evidence-based procedures that were advised by the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP). Younger women are heavily impacted by the advice and support they get from their partners, moms, and peers when it comes to nursing.

Conclusion

Preliminary research shows that at the gynecology ward at Marks Medical College and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, there was good awareness about breastfeeding exclusively from the mothers in this study. The average age of the 115 respondents was 25.47 SD 3.447, with the majority of those in the 23-27-year-old range. Respondents in this survey were well-educated and financially secure. 74.8 percent of the participants in this survey were familiar with the term 'exclusive breastfeeding and its benefits. Study participants were most likely to have received antenatal breastfeeding advice from their antenatal clinic and a family member. 85.2 percent of respondents gave their newborns liquid breast milk during the first three days of their lives. Many participants in this study strongly agreed that breast milk should be fed to a newborn, 84.3 percent agreed that it protects the baby from illness, and 68.7 percent agreed that it should be given to the baby as the first feed after birth. Moreover, 70.4 percent of participants said that breast milk alone can sustain a baby for six months. And as a result of this research, it can be concluded that most mothers at the Marks Medical College and Hospital Gynecology Ward had a strong understanding of exclusive breastfeeding.

Recommendations

- ❖ Exclusive breastfeeding counseling during antenatal clinics should be more collaborative with an emphasis on its advantage.
- ❖ Maximize opportunities for integrating breastfeeding campaigns. These should be done by all the stakeholders; Ministry of Health, NGOs, and others.
- ❖ Government should initiate all necessary measures to support and sustain exclusive breastfeeding.
- ❖ There should be public awareness of exclusive breastfeeding through television, radio, newspaper, and other media.
- ❖ Mass awareness programs should be arranged on exclusive breastfeeding.
- ❖ Arranging paper and poster for giving information about exclusive breastfeeding.
- ❖ A study on large sample size is recommended to assess the level of knowledge on exclusive breastfeeding.
- ❖ Women should be thought how to breastfeed and maintain exclusive breastfeeding.

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